

Horticultural Temporal Fruit Tracking via 3D Instance Segmentation and Re-Identification

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Abstract—Robotic fruit monitoring is crucial for automating agricultural systems, offering precise, high-throughput assessments that address the limitations of manual methods. Monitoring is challenging due to variations in fruit size, shape, orientation, and occlusion. Most methods rely on 2D images, that lack 3D structure and depth. While 3D colored point clouds provide this information, they introduce challenges like sparsity and irregularity. We propose a novel method for temporal fruit monitoring using point clouds collected over time. Experiments on a strawberry dataset show that this method outperforms baselines for temporal fruit monitoring in real-world scenarios.

Index Terms—Robotics and Automation in Agriculture, Agricultural Automation, Deep Learning for Visual Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for food calls for advancements in agricultural practices, focusing on efficiency and sustainability. Autonomous robots can automate labor-intensive tasks like crop monitoring and management. Temporal fruit re-identification, combined with accurate segmentation, enables tracking individual fruit growth over time, allowing for the analysis of growth patterns and maturation rates.

This paper focuses on tracking fruits in a greenhouse using colored point clouds from a robot equipped with a high-resolution LiDAR scanner. We propose a novel method for segmenting and matching individual fruits over time in 3D space. This is challenging because fruits vary in size, shape, orientation, and occlusion, and can be harvested or new.

We claim that our method (i) successfully identifies fruits in point clouds via instance segmentation and (ii) outperforms baseline methods in re-identification using real data.

II. OUR APPROACH

A. Fruit Instance Segmentation

Consider a colored point cloud \mathcal{P} in which each point has six features: the 3D position and the RGB color. We want to segment \mathcal{P} into a set $\mathcal{F} = \{\mathcal{F}_i\}_{i=1}^K$ of K fruit instances. Each $\mathcal{F}_i \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ can be described by the pair (\mathbf{c}_i, r_i) , where $\mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the center of the fruit and r_i is the radius of the smallest sphere, centered at \mathbf{c}_i , containing all the fruit's points.

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Fig. 1. Fruit re-identification on three point clouds at three points in time.

We use MinkPanoptic [2], a learning-based instance segmentation method, to obtain the fruit instances in a point cloud. MinkPanoptic first infers semantic segmentation, dividing points into fruit and background classes. Then, for each inferred fruit point, it predicts a 3D vector representing the point's offset from the center of the fruit instance it belongs to. We determine fruit instances \mathcal{F} by clustering the offset point cloud using the mean shift [3] algorithm.

B. Fruit Descriptor Extraction

The fruit descriptor extraction module, depicted on top of Fig. 2, processes fruit instances and computes their descriptors. Given a fruit \mathcal{F}_i and its center \mathbf{c}_i , we define with $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ the support of \mathcal{F}_i with fixed radius s :

$$S_i = \{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P} \mid \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{c}_i\|_2 \leq s\}. \quad (1)$$

First, S_i is voxelized using a fixed voxel size v . Then, a MinkowskiNet [4] encoder processes the voxelized point cloud by leveraging sparse 3D convolutions, capturing multi-scale features through a deep hierarchical structure. The encoder is composed of multiple stages that progressively downsample the input spatial dimensions while increasing the number of feature channels. After L identical blocks, we apply a global average pooling, which aggregates features across all the voxels obtaining the fruit's descriptor $\mathbf{d}_i \in \mathbb{R}^z$.

By computing the descriptors of all the fruits \mathcal{F} , we build a set of descriptors $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathbf{d}_1, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{|\mathcal{F}|}\}$ where \mathbf{d}_i represents the descriptor of fruit \mathcal{F}_i .

C. Fruit Descriptors Matching

The fruit descriptors matching module, depicted in Fig. 2 below, operates on sets of descriptors of fruits that belong to different time steps, e.g. \mathcal{D}^t of fruits $\mathcal{F}^t = \{\mathcal{F}_1^t, \dots, \mathcal{F}_A^t\}$ at time t , and \mathcal{D}^{t-1} of $\mathcal{F}^{t-1} = \{\mathcal{F}_1^{t-1}, \dots, \mathcal{F}_B^{t-1}\}$ at time $t-1$.

Fig. 2. The fruit descriptor extraction module processes a point cloud, voxelizes it, and uses a MinkowskiNet encoder with sparse 3D convolutions to compute the fruit descriptor. A global average pooling aggregates voxel features. The matching module matches this descriptor with others from different time points.

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED METHOD WITH BASELINES AT DIFFERENT IOU THRESHOLDS AND ON AVERAGE ON THE RE-IDENTIFICATION TASK. $F1_p$ AND $F1_n$ ARE THE COMMON F1 COMPUTED FOR POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE (NO-MATCH) CLASSES, RESPECTIVELY. ALL VALUES ARE IN %.

Approach	@5% IoU			@10% IoU			@25% IoU			avg		
	$F1_p$	$F1_n$	mF1									
Nearest Neighbor	76.1	14.3	45.2	73.8	11.5	42.7	58.6	6.5	32.6	69.5	10.8	40.2
Riccardi et al. [1]	56.1	19.6	37.9	52.1	19.7	35.9	43.6	13.9	28.7	50.6	17.7	34.2
Our approach	77.4	41.5	59.5	74.9	37.2	56.1	58.7	27.7	43.2	70.3	35.5	52.9

We want to match descriptors in \mathcal{D}^t with the corresponding descriptors in \mathcal{D}^{t-1} . We also want to label new fruits descriptors with a no-match label, \emptyset . Formally, we want to compute $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_A]^\top$ with $y_i \in \{\emptyset, 1, \dots, B\}$.

Let $\mathcal{F}_q^t \in \mathcal{F}^t$ be a query fruit point cloud. First, \mathbf{d}_q^t is concatenated to each descriptor in \mathcal{D}^{t-1} , obtaining the matrix $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 2z}$. To focus the module on the neighbors of the query fruit, we add a fixed positional encoding \mathbf{PE} to \mathbf{G} obtaining \mathbf{G}_e . To account for the no-match case, we append a new row in \mathbf{G}_e representing the no-match case, obtaining the matrix $\mathbf{G}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{(B+1) \times 2z}$. A linear layer, maps \mathbf{G}_p to $\mathbf{G}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(B+1) \times l}$, and a transformer encoder layer, processes \mathbf{G}_l obtaining $\mathbf{G}'_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(B+1) \times l}$. A final linear layer maps \mathbf{G}'_l to the prediction logits vector $\mathbf{p}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{B+1}$. These are normalized into a probability distribution \mathbf{p}_n by applying a softmax, then we mask it by setting the probability of fruits whose center is at a distance greater than h to 0 obtaining \mathbf{p} . The predicted matching fruit's index y_q is given by:

$$y_q = \begin{cases} i, & \text{if } i < B + 1 \\ \emptyset & \text{if } i = B + 1 \end{cases}, \text{ with } i = \underset{i}{\operatorname{argmax}}(\mathbf{p}) \quad (2)$$

By predicting y_i for each fruit in \mathcal{F}_i^t , we can associate each fruit in \mathcal{F}_i^t to fruits in \mathcal{F}_i^{t-1} with the vector \mathbf{y} . We compute the vector of associations \mathbf{y} using a greedy approach, starting by matching the most probable fruits first and removing them from the candidate pool.

D. Loss Function

We trained the fruit instance segmentation method following Marcuzzi et al. [2].

We trained our descriptor extraction and re-identification method end-to-end with a weighted loss function, \mathcal{L}_m , composed of two terms:

$$\mathcal{L}_m = \mathcal{L}_{ce} + \lambda_{inj} \mathcal{L}_{inj}. \quad (3)$$

\mathcal{L}_{inj} forces the network to learn a bijective function.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

For our experimental evaluation, we extend the dataset of Riccardi et al. [1], which consists of point clouds collected with a high-precision Faro Focus3D-X130 laser scanner in a commercial greenhouse, containing the same row of strawberries at 3 different points in time, each separated by approximately one week. Results, in Tab. I, demonstrate that our method outperforms baselines. An extended version of this system has been submitted to IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters [5].

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